

CURE KINETICS OF AN EPOXY WITH MIXED CURING AGENTS BY DSC DYNAMIC EXPERIMENT

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ABSTRACT

The curing kinetics of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A with a mixture of two diamines having different reaction rate was investigated by means of differential scanning calorimetry. Among various methods in determining kinetic parameters from multiple dynamic thermograms, Ozawa's and Kissinger's methods were employed to determine the activation energy and pre-exponential factor, respectively. It was found that the reaction rate was predominantly dependent upon the pre-exponential factor since there is no significant variation in activation energy when a mixture of diamines are used, and that the pre-exponential factor of the mixed curing system was inbetween those of single curing agent systems.

INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins have been widely used as a high performance thermosetting resin in many applications, such as coatings, adhesives, prepregs, paints, composites and others.¹⁻⁴ It is well known that an epoxy was modified with a large number of curing agents such as polyfunctional amines, alcohols, phenols, carboxylic acids, carboxylic anhydrides, Lewis acids and their complexes. The choice of particular crosslinking agents is dictated by end-use or service requirements. Given specific requirements, the usual approach is to formulate the systems based on empirically derived guidelines. Hence it seems to be very reasonable to use mixed curing agents of two or more to meet required physical or chemical properties. However, to our knowledge the curing behaviors of epoxy system by mixed curing agents have not been appeared on the literature.

There are several techniques to monitor the cure process such as d.c. conductivity, infrared absorption, dielectric spectroscopy⁵ and differential scanning calorimetry.^{6,7,8} In this study, the dynamic DSC method is employed to analyze the curing reaction of commercial diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A prepolymer with the stoichiometric mixtures of ethylene diamines and p-xylylene diamine or m-xylylene diamine as curing agents.

The ultimate goals of this study are to elucidate the changes of curing kinetics by DSC dynamic experiment when mixed curing agents are used, and to find any possibility whether the curing rate is controllable by mixed agents, particularly composed of two agents of different curing rates.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Materials

An epoxide resin used was commercial diglycidyl ether of Bisphenol A (DGEBA) (Kuk Do Chemical Company, epoxy equivalent weight, 190+5; $\bar{M}_n = 380$). Ethylene Diamine (EDA), p-xylene diamine (PXD) and m-xylene diamine (MXD) of reagent grade were used as an aliphatic and aromatic curing agents. All materials were used without further purification.

2. Preparation of formulations

Table 1 shows the amount of materials used in preparing formulations. All formulations were prepared in stoichiometric quantities since it has been reported that the maximum cross-link density is obtained at or slightly below stoichiometry^{9,10}. Each formulation was made by hand mixing for about five minutes.

Table 1. Preparations of DGEBA/diamines formulations of stoichiometric quantities

System	amount of DGEBA (g)	amount of diamines (g)
DGEBA/EDA	30.31	2.19 of EDA
DGEBA/PXD	35.40	6.45 of PXD
DGEBA/EDA-PXD	33.71	1.35 of EDA + 3.07 of PXD
DGEBA/MXD	35.67	6.50 of MXD
DGEBA/EDA-MXD	42.17	1.69 of EDA + 3.84 of MXD

3. Thermal Analysis

Thermal analyses were performed by du Pont 1090 thermal analyzer with a differential scanning calorimetry 910 module. For each formulation, nine to fourteen dynamic runs were executed at the heating rates between 2° and 80°C/min. The sample size was between 10 and 30mg, which was considered to be a compromise in an isothermal experiment. The heat of reaction was determined from the area under the exothermic cure curve.

THEORY

There have been several methods to extract kinetic information from dynamic DSC experiments. Among them, Ozawa's and Kissinger's methods, which have been known as a simple, yet accurate method, were used in this study.

Ozawa's method¹¹ is based on the assumption that the degree of cure at the peak temperature is constant and independent of heating rate. Assuming that the rate constant obeys the Arrhenius dependence upon temperature, the time derivative of the degree of cure can be expressed as eq. (1).

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = f(\alpha) A \exp(-E/RT) \quad (1)$$

where α is the degree of cure, $f(\alpha) = (1-\alpha)^n$, A the pre-exponential factor, and E the activation energy. Integration of eq. (1) proceeds as follows :

$$\int_0^{\alpha_p} \frac{d\alpha}{f(\alpha)} = A \int_{t_0}^{t_p} e^{-E/RT} dt \approx \frac{AE}{\phi_R} p(E/RT) \quad (2)$$

where ϕ is the heating rate, α_p the degree of cure at the peak exotherm and values for $P(E/RT)$ were tabulated by Doyle¹² for $20 < E/RT < 60$. The assumption of the constancy of α has been ascertained by many investigators.^{13,14} In this study, it was also assured as shown at Table 2. This assumption makes the left hand side of eq.(2) constant and eq.(3) is obtained from two pairs of heating rate and peak temperatures.

$$\Delta(1/T_p) / \Delta(\ln \phi) = -R/1.052E \quad (3)$$

The activation energy can be obtained from the slope of a plot of $1/T_p$ vs. $\ln \phi$.

Table 2. The constancy of degree of cure at the peak

Heating rate (°C/min.)	DGEBA/EDA	DGEBA/PXD	DGEBA/EDA-PXD
2	0.510	-	-
5	0.514	0.561	0.526
8	-	0.568	0.526
10	0.511	0.552	0.531
15	-	-	0.523
20	-	-	0.539
30	-	0.575	-
40	0.503	0.583	-
50	0.504	-	0.527
80	0.504	0.566	-

In order to determine the pre-exponential factor, Kissinger's method¹⁵ in which the major assumption is based on the fact that the DSC peak corresponds to the maximum reaction rate was employed. A useful and accurate expression for the frequency factor for n-th order reactions was derived as eq.(4).

$$A = \frac{\phi E \exp(E/RT_p)}{RT_p^2 n(1-\alpha_p)^{n-1}} \approx \frac{\phi E \exp(E/RT_p)}{RT_p^2} \quad (4)$$

Kissinger argued that $n(1-\alpha_p)^{n-1} \approx 1$ and independent of heating rate. This was confirmed by others.¹³ The activation energy can be obtained from the slope of the plot of $1/T_p$ vs. $\ln(\phi/T_p^2)$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1 shows the typical mode of the shift of peak exotherm temperature to higher temperature with increasing the heating rate (ϕ).

Fig.1. Effect of heating rate on the DSC exotherms with DGEBA-EDA. a; 10°C, b; 20°C, c; 30°C/min.

It has been observed that the peak temperature is independent of the degree of cure. Hence Ozawa's method has an advantage compared with isothermal methods which are very sensitive to the degree of cure of the sample. The peak exotherm temperature (T_p) and the reaction enthalpy (ΔH) of several epoxies are listed for seven heating rates in Table 3.

Table 3. The variations of peak exotherm temperatures (T_p) with heating rates (ϕ) and heats of reactions (ΔH)

Heating rates (°C/min.)	DGEBA/EDA		DGEBA/PXD		DGEBA/EDA-PXD		DGEBA/MXD		DGEBA/EDA-MXD	
	T_p (°C)	ΔH (J/G)								
5	84.5	409	90.3	427	89.8	480	94.6	-	91.5	428
8	93.1	407	97.2	413	98.7	486	99.6	-	99.2	420
10	96.8	405	104.9	448	103.5	475	107.3	-	106.4	-
15	106.6	396	112.8	412	111.0	446	115.1	-	113.1	428
20	109.8	369	120.8	413	116.1	461	125.0	457	122.1	420
30	121.5	396	132.7	427	125.3	-	134.1	-	131.1	408
50	133.4	362	143.5	399	143.9	461	145.1	-	144.5	407

The peak exotherm temperature for DGEBA/xylylene diamine is higher than for DGEBA/ethylene diamine system, and the temperature for DGEBA/mixed curing agent system is intermediate between two cure systems. However the difference of cure temperature between the two system is not so great, since the methylene group in xylylene diamine gives some aliphatic character to the compound.

Figures 2 and 3 are the plots of $1/T_p$ vs. $\ln \phi$ for six curing systems. It can be seen that good linearities and there are no significant differences of the slope one another. Almost the same slope for those systems explains that the activation energy for the curing reaction of epoxies should be dependent only on the type of functional group of the curing agent. The plots of $1/T_p$ vs. $\ln(\phi/T_p^2)$ for the application of Kissinger's method are shown in Figures 4 and 5. The similar tendencies to Figures 2 and 3 are observed.

Table 4 show the kinetic results from DSC dynamic experiments according to Ozawa's and Kissinger's method.

Table 4. Kinetic results from DSC dynamic experiments according to Ozawa's and Kissinger's method

System	Method I			Method II		
	E_a (kcal/mol)	A (sec ⁻¹)	k (sec ⁻¹)	E_a (Kcal/mol)	A (sec ⁻¹)	k (sec ⁻¹)
DGEBA/EDA	12.702	23.74x10 ⁴	0.03694	11.875	7.16x10 ⁴	0.03107
DGEBA/PXD	11.054	1.67x10 ⁴	0.01996	10.040	0.39x10 ⁴	0.01630
DGEBA/EDA-PXD	12.639	17.02x10 ⁴	0.02876	11.779	5.00x10 ⁴	0.02442
DGEBA/MXD	12.590	12.69x10 ⁴	0.02279	11.711	3.68x10 ⁴	0.01953
DGEBA/EDA-MXD	11.950	5.76x10 ⁴	0.02281	11.015	-	-

In method I, the activation energy was obtained from Ozawa's method, while the pre-exponential factor was obtained from Kissinger's method in which the activation energy from Ozawa's was used. In method II, both the activation energy and pre-exponential factor were obtained according to Kissinger's method. In determining the activation energy, the correlation coefficient of a linear regression line of Ozawa's method was always better than that of Kissinger's. Hence it is believed that the activation energy from Ozawa's method is more reliable.

Fig. 2 The plots of T_p versus $\ln \phi$. \blacktriangle ; DGEBA/EDA
 \blacksquare ; DGEBA/PXD
 \bullet ; DGEBA/EDA-PXD

Fig. 3. The plots of T_p versus $\ln \phi$. \blacktriangle ; DGEBA/EDA
 \blacksquare ; DGEBA/MXD
 \bullet ; DGEBA/EDA-MXD

Fig. 4. The plots of T_p versus $\ln(\phi/T_p^2)$. \blacktriangle ; DGEBA/EDA
 \blacksquare ; DGEBA/PXD
 \bullet ; DGEBA/EDA-PXD

Fig. 5. The plots of T_p versus $\ln(\phi/T_p^2)$. \blacktriangle ; DGEBA/EDA
 \blacksquare ; DGEBA/MXD
 \bullet ; DGEBA/EDA-MXD

As shown in Table 4, the activation energy lies in the range between 11 and 13 Kcal/mol, which is consistent with values obtained by isothermal method. Since there is no significant variations in activation energies, the reaction rate should be largely dependent on the pre-exponential factor A. The DGEBA/EDA system has the largest value of pre-exponential factor and the DGEBA/PXD the smallest one. In other words, the mobility of EDA is much better than that of PXD. The value of pre-exponential factor of the mixed curing system was inbetween those of single curing agent systems. Therefore the rate constants at 135°C show the same tendency as the pre-exponential factor.

CONCLUSIONS

The cure temperature for DGEBA/xylylene diamine is higher than for DGEBA/ethylene diamine system, and the temperature for DGEBA/mixed curing agent system is intermediate between two single cure systems. Since there is no significant variations in activation energies for all the systems examined, the reaction rate should be largely dependent upon the pre-exponential factor.

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